

Storage back-ends for Scalable Sync & Share based on Seafile

Maciej Brzeźniak, Krzysztof Wadówka, Paweł Wozzuk, Norbert Meyer
HPC Department, Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center
Jana Pawła II 10, 61-139 Poznań, Poland
{maciekb,kwadowka,pwozzuk,meyer}@man.poznan.pl

Abstract. In our paper we analyse scalability of the storage back-ends for Seafile, an efficient and reliable sync & share solution. Our considerations are conducted in the light of the requirements of the countrywide sync & share service deployed by PSNC for Polish academic community. We target large user base holding millions of files. We must also address high demand on efficiency for both large audience use cases and demanding scientific applications. In the paper we present and analyse the results of the benchmarks of the Seafile servers with GPFS and Ceph back-ends and draw conclusions related to the storage systems selection and setup for the large-scale storage service.

Introduction

With the growing data volumes handled by institutions and individuals, providing efficient and reliable data management becomes challenging. Analyst companies, including IDC, predict that by 2020 IT professionals will store 1.2TB per person in average. In fact power users of our sync & share service, e.g. physicists at Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań, already store 500+GB of data per account.

Sync & share service provided by HPC Department of PSNC in Poland targets a large user base including scientists, university staff, R&D projects participants and students. We expect several thousands of users and hundreds millions of files comprising hundreds of TBs. In order to address the requirements on volume and performance as well as ensure reliability of the service we chosen Seafile [1] a specialized solution designed for synchronization and sharing. Conceptually, the data model of Seafile is similar to Git [2]. Seafile employs filesystem snapshots mechanism rather than per-file versioning used in other solutions. It uses content-defined chunking for data de-duplication and client-server traffic optimization. Metadata stored by Seafile in the DBMS are limited to sharing information, user profiles and libraries' head commit IDs, which makes Seafile independent of the DBMS scalability. Actual data and meta-data are organised into libraries, similarly to Git repositories. Seafile's low-level implementation in C enables achieving high performance of synchronisation, upload and download while keeping the server and client CPU load low. Our tests performed in 2016 [3] showed that Seafile is 22-23x faster than other popular on-premise sync & share solutions while synchronising complex datasets, e.g. a Linux kernel source (50+k files and 3+k directories). As such Seafile has capability to stress the I/O subsystem, so it is an interesting killer application for the storage back-ends.

Storage back-ends for Seafile: GPFS and Ceph

In our work we evaluated Seafile with two storage systems that are representative for HPC data centres and cloud environments in academia, i.e. GPFS and Ceph. GPFS [3] is a reliable, scalable and high-performance clustered filesystem used in HPC environments for users' home directories and as a computing cluster scratch space. Ceph [4] is a popular, scalable and reliable object storage system. It is used as a cost-effective solution for storing large data volumes through its native RADOS interface (with librados) or through the S3 gateway. It

also provides block storage volumes for many OpenStack installations (through the RBD client).

Seafile supports various back-ends including GPFS (POSIX plugin) and Ceph (librados plugin). The decision on choosing and configuring storage system for the projected scale is not trivial. While data storage and access performance is an obvious measure, cost efficiency and maintenance complexity aspects have also to be taken into account. However, for the sake of conciseness in our paper we focus on performance scalability analysis.

Benchmarks

We conducted two kinds of benchmarks including upload and download of large files (1 file per client, 4480MB file) and small files (45 thousands of 100kB files per client) from the client to the Seafile server and opposite. The former test is representative for handling large multimedia, ISO images or research data. The latter simulated I/O traffic in general purpose sync & share applications where users deposit and exchange mainly documents, spreadsheets, text files and small pictures.

GPFS and Ceph have completely different architectures, so their configurations are hard to compare. Therefore for our tests we chosen the number of HDD drives in the disk array behind GPFS and in the Ceph disk servers as a reference parameter. In case of Ceph we used nine 12-disk servers, 2 Xeon E5 CPUs, 96 GB RAM and 2x dual 10GbE interface each, running Ceph Jewel (10.2.5). Storage configuration included 108 HDD-based OSDs and 2x replication. For GPFS we used two dual-socket servers with 128GB RAM, dual FC 16Gbit and dual 10GbE each, running GPFS v. 4.2.2. Storage configuration included midrange disk array with FC 16Gbit/s interconnects and twelve 10-disk RAID6 (8+2) groups. The GPFS filesystem was exported to the Seafile servers using NFSv3. We used Seafile Enterprise server v6.0.5.x86_64 in a cluster mode based on 2 dual socket servers, with Ubuntu 16.04.2 LTS, HAProxy, MariaDB and Memcached. Eight 2-socket servers were used to run Seafile clients (8-96 threads).

Figure 1 presents the results of the experiments. Left side charts show performance of large files upload and download expressed in MB/s. Right side drawings depict small files handling speed expressed in files per second.

If large files are considered, two trends are clearly visible. For uploads, back-ends differ significantly with GPFS reaching up to 3x higher performance than Ceph. This is related to the fact that in our configuration Ceph performs 2x replication while GPFS uses RAID6. Another reason for lower performance of Ceph is the overhead of storing the

data objects on the Seafile server's disks before ingesting them to RADOS cluster. Large files download speed with Ceph and GPFS is more comparable: differences fit within the range of 10% for most of the tests with an exception of 128-client benchmark where Ceph is 30% faster. It shows that Ceph is capable of efficiently streaming many large objects in parallel.

In the small files test, Ceph back-end proves to be slower for both uploads and multi-threaded downloads. Upload results (GPFS 1.5-3x faster than Ceph) are in-line with our expectations since Seafile's Ceph plugin requires an intermediate storage step while uploading the data. Ceph in turn performs additional writes for data replication, which we assume to happen partially asynchronously thanks to caching of writes using large RAM memory in Ceph servers (~1TB accumulated).

For downloads, we observe an interesting phenomenon. While for less than 32 threads Ceph is much faster than GPFS (even up to 2x), GPFS takes the lead for 32+ threads, achieving up to 1.9x better performance for 128 clients. In that case lower I/O latency of GPFS compared to Ceph helps Seafile to achieve better results with GPFS.

Analysis

We expect users of the sync & share service system to store mainly small files. Taking this into account and based on observations of Seafile server I/O patterns we assume that the real-life workload at the storage back-end will be dominated by small requests. Our tests show that under such kind of load GPFS performs faster and is more predictable, i.e. scales linearly with the growing number of Seafile clients. Opposite, Ceph demonstrated higher latency under a multi-threaded workload and less consistent performance scalability under parallel load.

In scientific applications percentage of large files may be higher than in general-purpose use case. Under such a workload both back-ends perform similarly. While it is visible that Ceph suffers from the data replication while uploading, we must admit that this problem can be partially mitigated by using erasure coding instead of full

objects replication (erasure coding with factor of 4:3 or 5:4 would ensure similar data redundancy to RAID6: 8+2). Overall, based on observations from our benchmarks we conclude that performance-wise GPFS will be more suitable back-end storage system for our large-scale, sync & share service as GPFS performance is better in most cases and it scales more linearly and predictably.

For PSNC, GPFS is also a natural choice for large-scale deployment of the data management system. While running Seafile with GPFS we can re-use our knowledge related to GPFS configuration, tuning, error handling and disaster recovery gathered while operating high-performance storage for HPC at PSNC and countrywide long-term storage system for academia in Poland.

Thanks to the fact that Seafile supports migration from the filesystem to Ceph back-end, while choosing GPFS now, we keep the option to switch to Ceph in future. Such change can be performed e.g. in the situation where the storage capacity cost or GPFS licensing cost become important part of the service operation budget or starts to be blocking factor of the further service development.

Acknowledgements

We would like to express our gratitude to Jonathan Xu and Daniel Pan, the Seafile developers and founders, for their valuable feedback to our work and their comments on the testing system configuration and the benchmark results.

References:

- [1] Seafile server manual. <https://manual.seafile.com/>
- [2] Chacon S., Git Internals. Source code control and beyond. <https://github.com/pluralsight/git-internals-pdf>
- [3] Brzeźniak M., Jankowski G., Jankowski M. et al. First experience with Seafile sync & share solution. TNC'16. 12-16 June 2016. <https://tnc16.geant.org/getfile/2992>
- [4] Weil S., Brandt S., Miller E., Long D., Maltzahn C. Ceph: A Scalable, High-Performance Distributed File System.
- [5] Schmuck F., Haskin R.. GPFS: A Shared-Disk File System for Large Computing Clusters. Proceedings of the FAST 2002 Conference Monterey, California, USA. January 28-30, 2002

Figure 1. Performance test results for Seafile server with GPFS and Ceph